

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Sulphones. Part IV.* Effect of *ortho*-Substituents

V. Baliah and T. Rangarajan

Several aryl methyl sulphones have been prepared and their ultraviolet absorption spectra recorded and analysed. Bulky *ortho*-substituents do not seem to cause any significant inhibition of conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the benzene nucleus in the electronically excited state. Ultraviolet absorption spectra of many substituted diaryl sulphones have also been recorded and analysed.

Methyl phenyl sulphone has a weak benzenoid band in the 250-270 m μ region and a strong band with maximum at 217 m μ (Fig. 1). The benzenoid band shows four absorption maxima

FIG. 1

due to vibrational transitions. The more intense band is presumably a K-band and it may be attributed to an electronically excited state receiving a contribution from structure (I).

(I)

The absorption spectra of a number of aryl methyl sulphones have been recorded in the present investigation with a view to studying the effect of *ortho*-substituents on the electronic interaction of the sulphonyl group with the benzene nucleus in the excited state. The data are recorded in Table I (see also Figs. 1-3).

TABLE I
UV absorption spectra of aryl methyl sulphones, ArSO₂Me.

Ar.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	Ar.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
Phenyl	271m μ	700	2,6-Dimethylphenyl	278m μ	2,400
	264	900		219	7,400
	258	600	2,6-Dimethoxyphenyl	294	4,700
	253	380		232	4,100
	217	7,100			
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	277	1,450	2,4-Dimethylphenyl	270	1,000
	270	1,700		227	10,150
	219	7,200			
<i>p</i> -Tolyl*	273	460	3,4-Dimethylphenyl	269	850
	267	540		227	10,000
	262	560	2,5-Dimethylphenyl	276	1,700
	257	450		220	7,900
	225	11,750			
<i>o</i> -Butyl ^l phenyl	278	1,450	2,5-Diethylphenyl	283	1,800
	272	1,700		276	1,900
	222	7,200		221	9,000
Mesityl*	285	1,800	2,5-Dibutyl ^l phenyl	272	900
	280	1,600		265	850
	277	1,700		224	13,200
	230	8,900			

* Data from Fehnel and Carmack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1296.

While analysing the spectral data in relation to conjugation, we have to consider only the intense K-band, which is due to conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the benzene nucleus. It may be readily seen that a *p*-methyl group causes a bathochromic shift of the absorption maximum as well as an increase in intensity of the band while an *o*-methyl group does not seem to have any significant effect. The spectrum of *o*-butyl^lphenyl methyl sulphone is almost like that of methyl *o*-tolyl sulphone, the bulkiness of the *o*-butyl^l group having no appreciable effect. Even in a compound like 2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone, the two *o*-methyl groups are not seen to inhibit conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the benzene nucleus. When a carbonyl or a nitro group conjugates with the benzene nucleus, coplanarity of the atoms (C and O or N, O and O) with the benzene nucleus is necessary if there is to be effective π -orbital interaction (cf. Braude and Sondheimer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3754; Wepster, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1957, 76, 335).

When conjugation with the sulphonyl group occurs, the situation is different. Sulphur can expand its valence shell by utilising its vacant *d*-orbitals. If we consider the ground state of

2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone, structure (II) may be assumed to contribute chiefly to it.

FIG. 2

The four valence bonds in (II) result from $3s3p^3$ hybridisation. The bonds may be taken as essentially tetrahedral. Structure (III) makes a significant contribution to the excited state. The four σ -bonds in it are still tetrahedral. The π -bond seems to be possible by the overlapping of the $2p$ -orbital of carbon and the $3d$ -orbital of sulphur. In that case planarity of the atoms in the sulphonyl group with the benzene nucleus is not necessary for conjugation (see also Fehnel and Carmack, *loc. cit.*). Thus the absence of steric inhibition of conjugation in the excited state of 2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone becomes clear.

The absorption spectra of many diaryl sulphones were also taken in the present study with a view to examining polar and steric effects. The data are shown in Table II.

FIG. 3

TABLE II

UV absorption spectra of diaryl sulphones.

Sulphone.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	Sulphone.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .		
Diphenyl (D)	274m μ	1,450	2-Methyl-4'-methoxy-D	252m μ	18,700		
	266	2,100	2,2'-Dimethyl-4-methoxy-D	253	18,000		
	260	1,800					
	235	17,400	2-Methoxy-5,2'-dimethyl-D	298	4,400		
* 2-Methyl-D	266.5	2,000	223	18,400			
	273.5	2,200	2-Methoxy-4,2'-dimethyl-D	289	4,900		
	234.0	14,100				240	12,900
* 4-Methyl-D	274	1,350	2-Methoxy-4-methyl-D	291	5,600		
	266	2,350				241	14,700
	241	18,200	2-Methoxy-4,4'-dimethyl-D	290	5,000		
2,6-Dimethyl-D	280	2,300				244	16,400
	235	12,850				226	16,700
2,6,2'-Trimethyl-D	279	3,000	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-D	298	4,300		
	233	13,400				221	20,700
2,6,2',6'-Tetramethyl-D	286	3,400	2-Methoxy-5,4'-dimethyl-D	298	4,450		
	279	3,550				238	14,700
	234	13,600				226	18,700
2-Methoxy-D	290	4,600	2,4-Dimethoxy-D	287	7,150		
	235	12,000				252	14,800
	219	16,400				2,6-Dimethoxy-D	300
3-Methoxy-D	290	3,100	248	9,700			
	275	2,400	2,6,2',6'-Tetramethoxy-D	293	7,700		
	224	18,100				252	15,100
4-Methoxy-D	254	18,000					
2-Methyl-4-methoxy-D	253	16,900					

* Data from Leandri *et al.*, *Gazzetta*, 1954, 84, 73.

The K-band of diphenyl sulphone has maximum at 235 m μ . This band may be attributed to the conjugation of the sulphonyl group with the two benzene nuclei. It undergoes displacement towards longer wave length with increase in intensity when a methyl or a methoxyl group is present *para* to the sulphonyl group. This is in agreement with the view that in the case of *para*-disubstituted benzene derivatives, if the two groups enhance the tendency for electron transfer in the same direction, a bathochromic shift occurs. When a methyl group is present in the *para* position, the 235 m μ band is seen to shift to the 240-245 m μ region; in the case of a *p*-methoxy sulphone the band shifts to the 250-255 m μ region.

The presence of one or more *o*-methyl groups does not significantly alter the absorption maximum, but there is a reduction in intensity (see Fig. 4).

FIG. 4

The presence of one *o*-methoxyl group does not alter the absorption maximum, but when more methoxyl groups are present in the *ortho* position a bathochromic shift occurs, there being reduction in the intensity of absorption in all cases. The *ortho* effects, observed in diaryl sulphones, are thus somewhat different from those observed in aryl methyl sulphones. An explanation was offered by Baliah and Ramakrishnan (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 151) for some of the *ortho* effects seen in diaryl sulphones.

Some of the spectral data recorded in Table II can be explained on the basis that the methoxyl or methyl group is forced out of the plane of the benzene ring when present *ortho* to a sulphonyl group. For example, in 2-methoxydiphenyl sulphone there seem to be two electronic excitations: (1) the methoxyl group being forced out of the plane of the benzene ring, $-\text{SO}_2-$ conjugates with

the benzene nuclei, (2) the phenylsulphonyl group being forced out of the plane of the benzene ring, -OMe conjugates with the benzene nucleus. 2-Methoxydiphenyl sulphone exhibits three absorption maxima (λ_{max} 280, 273, 233 $m\mu$; ϵ_{max} 2500, 2700, 14500). The bands at 280 and 273 $m\mu$ may be ascribed to electronic excitation (2), described above (cf. the spectrum of anisole: λ_{max} 278, 271, 222 $m\mu$; ϵ_{max} 1400, 2100, 7300). The band at 233 $m\mu$ may be ascribed to electronic excitation (1) since diphenyl sulphone absorbs maximally at 235 $m\mu$.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Butylthiophenol.—Sulphuric acid (*d* 1.12, 120 c.c.) was added to *o*-butylaniline (Shoosmith and Mackie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2337 (10 g.) and the mixture was stirred well to ensure formation of finely divided amine sulphate. The contents of the flask were cooled to -12° in an ice-salt mixture. The amine sulphate was diazotised with a cold solution of sodium nitrite (10 g.) in water (20 c.c.). It was found necessary to maintain the temperature at -12° since the diazonium compound decomposed above -10° . The diazonium sulphate solution was then added to a solution of potassium ethyl xanthate (50 g.) and sodium carbonate (25 g.) in water (200 c.c.), kept at 70° . The mixture was heated on a water bath for 1 hour to complete the decomposition. The oil being settled was extracted with ether, washed with a 10% NaOH solution (20 c.c.) and then with water, and dried (CaCl_2).

After removal of the ether the xanthogenic ester was taken up in ethanol (95%, 200 c.c.) contained in a 1-litre r.b. flask, and refluxed. To the boiling solution were added potassium hydroxide pellets (40 g.) at such a rate that the hydrolysis did not become too vigorous. After the addition, the mixture was refluxed for 8 hours and as much of ethanol as possible was removed by distillation. The mixture was then acidified with H_2SO_4 (1:1, 50 c.c.), zinc dust (10 g.) was added, and distilled in steam until no more oily drops passed over. The distillate was extracted with ether and dried (CaCl_2). The thiophenol, that remained after removal of the ether, boiled at $84-86^\circ/10$ mm, yield 2.6 g. It has a highly unpleasant characteristic odour. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 8.55. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{S}$ requires C, 72.2; H, 8.5%).

o-Butylphenylmethyl Sulphide.—*o*-Butylthiophenol was methylated using methyl iodide in absolute ethanol containing sodium ethoxide. The mixture was left overnight, refluxed for 2 hours on a water bath, and poured into water. The oil separating was extracted with ether; the ether extract was first washed with a 10% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) and then with water, and dried (CaCl_2). After evaporation of the ether, the sulphide (2 g.) distilled at $118-20^\circ/7$ mm. (Found: C, 73.45; H, 9.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{S}$ requires C, 73.3; H, 8.9%).

o-Butylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—The foregoing sulphide in acetic acid was treated with a solution of KMnO_4 and left overnight. The excess of KMnO_4 and the precipitated MnO_2 were reduced with SO_2 and the clear solution was evaporated to dryness on a water bath. The residue was triturated thrice with acetone and the acetone was removed from the combined extracts. The separated oil soon solidified, m.p. $69-70^\circ$ (dilute ethanol), (Found: C, 62.4; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 62.2; H, 7.6%).

2,6-Dimethylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—2,6-Dimethylthiophenol (Kazimi *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2479) was methylated and the methyl sulphide was oxidised with KMnO_4 in acetic acid. The sulphone was obtained in 90% yield, m.p. 93-94°. Bolssens *et al.* (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1954, **73**, 836) report m.p. 94.5-95°.

2,5-Dimethylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—2,5-Dimethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride (Huntress and Autenrieth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3446) was reduced with zinc dust and water to afford sodium 2,5-dimethylbenzenesulphinate. The sulphinate (20 g.) was methylated with methyl iodide (16 g.) in absolute ethanol (75 c.c.). The yield of the sulphone was 6 g., m.p. 39-40° (dilute ethanol). (Found: C, 58.8; H, 6.5. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 58.7; H, 6.6%.)

2,4-Dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone was prepared from 2,4-dimethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride as in the previous case. After recrystallisation from dilute ethanol it melted at 55°. Tröger and Budde (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1902, **66**, 149) report the same m.p.

3,4-Dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone was also obtained from the corresponding sulphonyl chloride. It melted at 72-73° (dilute ethanol). (Found: C, 58.8; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 58.7; H, 6.6%.)

2,5-Dibutylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—Here again the starting material was the corresponding sulphonyl chloride. The sulphonyl chloride underwent reduction only after refluxing for 8 hours with zinc dust and water. The sulphinate on methylating with methyl iodide yielded the sulphone, m.p. 70-71° (ethanol-water). (Found: C, 67.2; H, 8.9. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 67.1; H, 9.0%.)

2,5-Diethylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—2,5-Diethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride, obtained by the chlorosulphonylation of *p*-diethylbenzene (Auwers, *Annalen*, 1919, **419**, 115), was reduced to the corresponding sodium sulphinate and methylated with methyl iodide. The sulphone boiled at 146-48°/6 mm. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 62.15; H, 7.6%.)

2,6-Dimethoxythiophenol.—2,6-Dimethoxyaniline (Kauffmann and Franck, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 4006) (15.3 g.) was diazotised and the diazonium solution was added to a solution of potassium ethyl xanthate (30 g.) and sodium carbonate (20 g.) in water (60 c.c.), maintained at 70°. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 2 hours. The xanthogenic ester was taken up in ether, washed with a 10% solution of NaOH (20 c.c.) and then with water, and dried (CaCl_2). The ether was removed and the xanthogenic ester was hydrolysed. The thiophenol was removed by steam distillation. After recrystallising from ethanol, the thiophenol (5.3 g.) melted at 85-86°. (Found: C, 56.9; H, 6.0. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 56.45; H, 5.9%.)

2,6-Dimethoxyphenylmethyl Sulphide.—Methylation of the foregoing thiophenol with methyl iodide in absolute ethanol solution containing sodium ethoxide furnished this sulphide in almost quantitative yield. On recrystallisation from ethanol it melted at 79-81°. (Found: C, 58.8; H, 6.7. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 58.7; H, 6.6%.)

2,6-Dimethoxyphenyl methyl sulphone was obtained by oxidising the above sulphide with hydrogen peroxide. It melted at 139-40° (water). (Found: C, 49.5; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 50.0; H, 5.6%.)

2,2',6,6'-Tetramethoxydiphenyl Sulphide.—To a solution of 2,6-dimethoxythiophenol (2.5 g.) in absolute ethanol (20 c.c.) sodium (0.4 g.) was added and the ethanol was distilled off. 2,6-Dimethoxyiodobenzene (Kauffmann and Franck, *loc. cit.*) (4 g.) and copper powder (0.2 g.) were added to the dry sodium salt of the thiophenol and the mixture was heated in an oil bath for 4 hours at 200-20°. After cooling, the mixture was triturated thrice with ethanol. H_2SO_4 (1:1; 20 c.c.) and zinc dust (5 g.) were added to the extract and the mixture was distilled in steam to remove the

unchanged thiophenol and the iodo compound. The solid in the flask was filtered and triturated several times with ethanol. Distillation of ethanol gave the sulphide (2.8 g.) which, after recrystallising eight times from acetic acid and finally from ethanol, melted at 152-54°. (Found: C, 62.8; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 62.7; H, 5.9%).

2,2', 6,6'-Tetramethoxydiphenyl Sulphone.—The foregoing sulphide (0.05 g.) in acetone was oxidised with hydrogen peroxide. The yield of the sulphone was 0.02 g. It was recrystallised from water, m.p. 175-76° (decomp.). (Found: C, 56.7; H, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6S$ requires C, 56.8; H, 5.4%).

2,2', 6,6'-Tetramethyldiphenyl Sulphide.—2,6-Dimethylthiophenol (0.1 M) and 2,6-dimethyl-iodobenzene (Kohlrausch and Pongratz, *Monatsh.*, 1934, 64, 369) (0.1 M) were added to a solution of sodium ethoxide (0.1 M) in absolute ethanol and the excess ethanol was removed. The mixture was heated at 250-60° for 4 hours in presence of copper powder. On working up the product in the usual way, the sulphide was obtained in 60% yield. Repeated recrystallisation from ethanol gave colorless prisms, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 79.2; H, 7.4. $C_{16}H_{18}S$ requires C, 79.3; H, 7.5%).

2,2',6,6'-Tetramethyldiphenyl Sulphone.—The foregoing sulphide on oxidation with $KMnO_4$ afforded the sulphone in 95% yield. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 6.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2S$ requires C, 70.0; H, 6.6%).

2,2',6-Trimethyldiphenyl sulphide was obtained from 2,6-dimethylthiophenol and *o*-iodotoluene in 60% yield, m.p. 89-90° (ethanol). (Found: C, 78.6; H, 7.05. $C_{15}H_{16}S$ requires C, 78.9; H, 7.1%).

2,2',6-Trimethyldiphenyl Sulphone.—Oxidation of the above sulphide with $KMnO_4$ yielded the sulphone, m.p. 104-105° (ethanol). (Found: C, 69.5; H, 6.3. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.2%).

2,6-Dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was obtained from 2,6-dimethylthiophenol and iodobenzene. The compound boiled at 142°/10 mm. Truce and Ray (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 481) report b.p. 112-22°/1 mm.

2,6-Dimethyldiphenyl Sulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide with $KMnO_4$ afforded this sulphone in 85% yield, m.p. 101-102° (ethanol). Truce and Ray (*loc. cit.*) report the same m.p.

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, model DU. The solvent used was 95% ethanol.